

Dynamic Relationship of Oil and Non-Oil Sectors' and Economic Growth in Nigeria: Markov-Switching VAR Analysis

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ABSTRACT

As Nigeria strives towards non-oil sector led growth through diversification, there is need to study the asymmetric growth impact of oil and non-oil sectors. Which of these sectors drive the economy during high growth regime and low growth regime? To answer this question, this study utilized quarterly data from 2010 to 2022 on real gross domestic product, oil sector, non-oil sector and money supply in a non-linear regime switching model. Markov-Switching Intercept VAR [MSIARH(2)-VAR(2)] model with two states – regime 1 (high growth) and regime 2 (low growth)- was estimated. The result indicated that both oil and non-oil sectors are positively related to high economic growth. Conversely, both oil and non-oil sectors are negatively related to low economic growth. The probability of staying in regime 1 is 53.4 percent while the probability of staying in regime 2 is 55 percent. This shows low growth persistence in the economy. The result also indicates that there is more likelihood of switching from high growth regime to low growth regime with longer low growth duration. We recommend the diversification of the economy to achieve sustainable growth through investments in the non-oil sectors.

Keywords: oil sector, non-oil sector, economic growth, Markov-switching

1.INTRODUCTION

Oil remains a strategic commodity in the global energy landscape and dominates the other internationally traded commodities. While the price of oil is prone to regular unanticipated fluctuations, the implications to the global economy have been a subject of extensive research (Hamilton, 2020). The shocks triggered by oil price fluctuations affect both oil-producing and oil-consuming nations which underscores the need for nuanced understanding of oil price volatility across the globe (Difeto et al., 2018; Kilian, 2016). Nigeria is an OPEC member nation and its economy is broadly classified into two – oil and non-oil sectors. Given the exposure of the economy to shocks emanating from international oil market and government's excessive dependence on revenue from oil export for its fiscal planning, there has been constant calls for a virile economic diversification (Difeto et al., 2018; Smith & Adeyemi, 2017). Several policies have been initiated towards attaining a sustainable non-oil led growth and earning of foreign exchange beyond the oil sector (Nwosu et al., 2020). Although, there is improved non-oil sectors performance in recent years, Nigeria is still exposed to oil price shocks which casts a lot of doubts on its economic diversification efforts (Iwayemi, 2018).

A plethora of research on the impact of non-oil sector on economic growth exists. Many of these studies on non-oil sector contribution to economic growth were conducted in disaggregated sectoral levels while others were conducted in aggregated sectoral level. The consensus of the findings in this regard support a positive relationship between non-oil sectors and economic growth (Akighir & Tarlumun, 2019; Ideh et al., 2021; Kenechukwu & Akujinma, 2022; Nwosu et al., 2020; Riti, 2016; Smith & Adeyemi, 2017). Contrarily, many studies on the impact of oil sector on economic growth focused on oil export and found the existence of positive relationships between oil export and economic growth (Obstfeld et al., 2016) while others

focused on oil price shocks and economic growth with conclusion of existence of negative relationship with economic growth in Nigeria (Nwosu et al., 2018, 2020)

At the disaggregated sectoral level, the oil sector (Crude petroleum and natural gas) component of the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) led other key non-oil sectors (Agriculture, Trade and Manufacturing) in terms of contribution to the GDP from 1981 until about 2010. See Figure 1 shows a five-year average of contributions of Agriculture, Trade and Manufacturing sectors and Crude petroleum and natural gas sector from 1981 to 2020 in billions of Naira. Between 1981 and 1985, the average contribution of Crude oil sector to the real GDP was N4,592.1 billion while the average contribution of Agriculture, Trade and Manufacturing sectors to the real GDP stood at N2,446.8, N1,761.8 and N4,219.5 billion respectively.

Figure 1: Five Years Average of Key Non-Oil Sectors and Oil Sector

Oil sector-led contribution to the real GDP continued until 2006 when the Agricultural sector overtook the oil sector. The average share of the Agricultural sector between 2006 and 2010 was N11,641.1 billion while Crude petroleum and natural gas followed with N8,336.1 billion. This was followed by the Trade sector with a value of N7,246.6 billion and the Manufacturing sector value at N3,339.9 billion. The economy experienced the dominance of Agricultural sector from 2015 till 2020 while the Manufacturing sector that should have been the engine of growth in a modern economy like Nigeria's continued to trail behind. Between 2016 and 2020, the average contribution of the non-oil sectors out-performed the oil sector as the Agriculture, Trade and Manufacturing sectors contributed N17,527.5 billion, N11,315.9 billion and N6,354.6 billion respectively while Crude petroleum and natural gas sector contributed N5,918 billion. This analysis shows an oil sector dominance in the making of the final GDP and further underscores the need for a virile diversification effort.

However at the aggregate level, between 2012 and 2022 the non-oil sector have contributed an average of about 91 percent to Nigeria's GDP while the oil sector contributed an average of 8.6 percent to Nigeria's GDP in the same period. Meanwhile, oil constituted Nigeria's major export commodity contributing an average of 90.1 percent to the export basket. In terms of revenue to the government, the oil sector contributed over 85 percent from 2000 to 2010. With improvements in the non-oil sectors performance and dwindling global demand for crude oil, the non-oil sectors' contribution to government grew from 20.1 percent in 2011 to 60 percent in 2022. In terms of growth rate, there has been a cyclical movement of both oil and non-oil sectors around GDP growth rate. Figure 2 shows the percentage growth rate of the real GDP, Oil and Non-oil sectors from 1981 to 2021. Expectedly, the growth rate of the real GDP and

aggregate Non-oil sectors co-moved together during the positive and negative growth rates while the oil sector growth rate was largely independent of the real GDP and the Non-oil sector.

Figure 2: % Annual Growth Rate of GDP, Oil and Non-oil Sectors

For instance, there was -1.1 percent growth rate of real GDP and -5.6 percent growth of the Non-oil sector in 1984 whereas the oil sector recorded a 12.5 percent growth. However, between 1986 and 1987, there were positive growth rates in both real GDP and Non-oil sector while the Oil sector recorded negative growth rates. A cursory look at Figure 2 reveal that there is asymmetric growth rates between the Oil sector and Non-oil sector around the real GDP growth trend. The implication of this is that both Oil and Non-oil sectors play significant roles in the Nigerian business cycle and both have contributed to economic growth at different rates.

Economic research is replete with studies on oil/non-oil-macroeconomy relationship both at the domestic and international space. In the non-oil-macroeconomy analysis, disaggregated sectors are mostly utilized. However, there is scarcity of studies focusing on impact of aggregated Non-oil sectors on economic growth. Similarly, studies on the relationship between oil and the economy focused on oil price and revenue aspects without considering oil output as a share of GDP. The contribution of crude oil and natural gas sector as GDP component cannot be ignored in oil-macroeconomy analysis if we are to unravel the diversification mystery. Majority of the previous studies adopted a linear model without considering the transition in the growth rate of the GDP despite evidence of high and low growth regimes. This is important because understanding economic transitions is a crucial component of policy making particularly for an oil dependent economy like Nigeria. Ignoring this transition may muddle our understanding of the true relationship between the real GDP and its major components. Which of these sectors drive the economy during high growth regime and low growth regime? What is the policy implication of the asymmetric growth path of these key sectors in different regimes? To answer this question, this estimated a non-linear regime switching model, that is, Markov-Switching Intercept VAR [MSIARH(2)-VAR(2)] model with two states – regime 1 (high growth) and regime 2 (low growth). Thus, the objective of this study is to analyse the impact of Oil and Non-oil sectors on economic growth in Nigeria in different states of the economy. Understanding the behaviour of both aggregate non-oil sector and the oil sector in the growth process will be crucial in the formulation of diversification policies. Studies that explored the asymmetric relationship between economic growth and other variables are sparse. Quarterly data analysis of oil and non-oil linkage to growth is nonexistent. These constituted a research gap that this study is trying to bridge.

The theoretical basis for this study is anchored on economic literature that emphasize the importance of understanding the asymmetric impact of different sectors on economic growth. This research recognizes the ongoing efforts towards non-oil sector-led growth through diversification. Non-linear regime switching models captures the distinct growth dynamics during periods of high and low growth in the economy. We further justified this approach because it aligns with economic theories that emphasizes the non-linear nature of economic processes and the need to consider regime-specific relationships. The rest of the study is organized as follows. Following section 1 introduction, section 2 presents literature review, section 3 is devoted to methodology, section 4 presents the empirical result, section five is devoted to policy implication of the study and conclusion. the paper.

2.LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Theoretical Review

Literature is replete with theories linking natural resource abundance and economic development. Many studies conclude that natural resource is detrimental to economic growth of host economies (Auty, 1993; Sachs & Andrew, 1997). Three of these theories related to this study were briefly reviewed.

2.1.1 Dutch Disease Hypothesis

The so called Dutch disease theory emanated from the failure of Dutch manufacturing sector following the discovery of natural gas. This theory suggests that a booming natural resource sector can cause a decline in the development of other tradable sectors particularly the manufacturing sector. This theory is anchored on the observation that the discovery of natural resources such as oil, can lead to the appreciation of the exchange rate which makes the non-resource exports to be less competitive leading to a decline in the manufacturing sector (Sachs & Andrew, 1997). The consequence from this theory leads to a lack of diversification and dependence on the natural resource sector. This negatively affects long-term economic growth particularly for developing countries that lack the institutional capacity to effectively manage the resource sector to promote economic diversification (Beck, 2011)

2.1.2 Resource Curse Theory or the paradox of plenty

The resource curse theory states that countries endowed with abundant natural resources suffer retarded economic development (Auty, 1993). This theory posits that countries with abundant natural resource such as oil face inhibited economic development, governance problems, higher incidence of armed conflicts and preponderance of political instability. This theory is anchored on the observation that resource-rich countries experience challenges in diversifying their economies which leads to over-dependence on the resource sector and neglect of other sectors. This corroborates Nigerian economic history following the discovery of oil in commercial quantity which led to the neglect of agriculture and manufacturing. This led to economic underperformance. The implication of resource curse theory lies in the economic backwardness emanating from excessive dependence on natural resources as against a diversified economy. This further emphasizes the importance of economic diversification to mitigate the negative effects of resource curse (Satti et al., 2014).

2.1.3 Economic Diversification Theory or Structural Transformation Theory

Following history evidence, modern economic growth relies on structurally transforming the economy by reallocation of economic activity across broad sectors such as agriculture, manufacturing and services (Kuznets, 1973). This theory explains that a sustained economic

development follows the transformation from traditional agrarian economic base to a more diverse and modern industrialized and service based economy. This transformation requires the reallocation of labor and capital from low-productivity sectors such as agriculture to high-productivity sectors like manufacturing and services (Syrquin, 1988). This theory emphasizes the importance of economic diversification to decrease exposure to external shocks, enhance productivity and promote sustained growth. For resource-rich developing countries like Nigeria that operates at the agricultural and extractive productive level, transforming to modern industrial sector will not only enhance growth but makes for a more competitive productivity. In the context of this study, undiversified economic structure encourages overreliance on single commodity which increases vulnerability to external shocks and impedes economic growth.

2.2 Empirical Review

The linkage between oil and economic activities has been a subject of extensive study for many decades. The role of oil as a major energy source in the production process has already been established. Similarly, there are many studies in economic literature on non-oil sector and its relationship with economic growth. Most of the studies on non-oil sector and growth followed the disaggregated approach using sectorial share of GDP as proxy while others utilized non-oil exports revenue. In what follows, an attempt is made to review recent studies on oil and non-oil impact on economic growth. Riti, et al (2016) examined the growth of non-oil sectors as key to diversification and economic performance in Nigeria. They estimated an ARDL model while utilizing data on agric, manufacturing and telecommunication sectors. Their result indicates the existence of a long-run relationship between non-oil sectors and economic growth. Balcilar et al., (2017) analyzed the impact of oil price on GDP for South African economy using quarterly data from 1960 to 2013. They estimated a two regime Bayesian MS-VAR model. Their result indicates that there is persistence of high growth regime than the low growth regime.

On their part, Nwosu et al., (2018) studied the impact of oil price shock on industrial production using monthly data between 1981 and 2015. An EGARCH model was used to extricate positive fluctuations in oil price and a Bayesian Vector Autoregressive model was estimated. Their result showed the existence of positive and favourable relationship between increases in the oil price and industrial production in Nigeria. Accordingly, Akighir & Tarlumun, (2019) studied the impact of non-oil exports and economic growth in selected African countries (Algeria, Angola, Cameroun, Chad, Egypt, Equatorial Guinea, Ghana, Libya, Republic of Congo, Nigeria and Sudan) from 1986 to 2018 while implementing a dynamic panel data model. Their result reveal that there is a positive relationship between non-oil export and economic growth in majority of the countries included in the study. Nwosu et al., (2020) further examined the effect of oil price shocks on the real sectors of the Nigerian economy in a vector autoregressive modelling (VAR) framework using agricultural sector output, industrial sector output, manufacturing sector output, money supply and Oil price while utilizing annual data spanning between 1981 and 2018. Their result showed that there was a long run negative impact of oil price shocks on the real sectors of the Nigerian economy. Olowo et al., (2020) examined sectorial contributions of non-oil revenue to economic growth in Nigeria using data from 1981 to 2018 on the following variables- environmental, information and communication technology, financial sectors revenue and real GDP. They estimated an ARDL model and found that environmental, information and communication technology, financial sectors revenue are positively related to economic growth. Similarly, Agu et al., (2020) investigated the nexus between non-oil export and economic Growth in Nigeria using data (1986-2018) on the following variables- real GDP, non-oil export, labor force, interest rate and exchange rate. An ARDL model was estimated while the result reveal that there is negative impact of non-oil sector on economic growth

in the short run but a positive relationship in the long run. Ideh et al., (2021) examined the relationship between non-oil sector and economic growth in Nigeria using data from 2000 to 2019 on agric, solid mineral, trade, services sectors and real GDP. They estimated a VAR model and found that there were negative relationships between agric, solid mineral and trade while services sector was positively related economic growth in Nigeria. On their part, Kenekwue & Akujinma, (2022) examined the impact of non-oil export on Nigerian economic growth in a disaggregate approach using vegetable exports, textiles export, animal exports, agricultural raw materials exports, solid minerals exports and the GDP. The model of this study was Vector Autoregressive Estimates model and they found that non-oil exports has positive but insignificant effect on economic growth in Nigeria economy.

Osintseva, (2022) examined the influence of oil prices and changes in oil production on economic growth in oil-exporting countries. The study utilized a Dynamic heterogeneous panel PMG estimation method on linear and non-linear models to ascertain the threshold level where an increase beyond which oil will no longer contribute to the economic growth of these countries. The study concluded that economic growth in these countries largely depend on increases in oil prices and changes in oil production rates. Based on the literature reviewed so far, it can be seen that most oil and non-oil studies ignored oil output (percentage of GDP) or the aggregate of the key non-oil sectors (Agric, Manufacturing and Trade). Thus, we explored this line for this current study.

3. Methodology

3.1 Model Specification of Markov Switching VAR

Recent developments in econometrics indicate the presence of regime shifts in time series data. Markov Switching VAR Model (MS-VAR) model captures these regime shifts by allowing for the identification of distinct states or regimes where the relationships between variables can vary (Hamilton, 1989; Primiceri, 2005). The model's ability to capture the shifts in the underlying structure of an economy makes it more useful to analyze the dynamic nature of economic transitions. In this study, we assume the presence of different regimes and the transition between regimes is governed by a Markov process. Understanding economic transitions is a crucial component of policy making particularly for an oil dependent economy like Nigeria. Thus, we employed the MS-VAR model to discern the different regimes that characterize economic growth and assess the impact of oil sector and non-oil sector on the regimes.

The MS-VAR model assumes different regimes or states identified by examining the probabilities assigned to each state over time. The dynamics of variables in each regime is then examined by checking the estimated parameters for each regime to understand how variables respond to shocks in different states and how the coefficients change across regimes. Next the state transition probabilities are evaluated between regimes. Higher transition probabilities show a higher likelihood of moving from one regime to another. Then impulse response analysis for each regime is conducted to understand the effects of shocks and compare how variables respond differently in different states. Sims (1980) proposed a standard VAR model of K-dimensional time series vector $y_t = (y_{1t}, \dots, y_{Kt})$ specified as

$$y_t = \alpha + A_1 y_{t-1} + \dots + A_p y_{t-p} + \varepsilon_t \quad (1)$$

Where $t = 1, \dots, T$, α is a vector of intercepts and A_i are coefficient matrices. ε_t is the unobservable error process which is white noise zero mean process. The major drawback of this Sims, (1980) type of model is its linearity and parameter time-invariance. A regime switching model handles the non-linearity and time-varying parameters in economic time series. If y_t

is defined conditional upon the regime $s_t \in \{1, \dots, M\}$, the probability density function of the vector of endogenous variables $y_t = (y_{1t}, \dots, y_{K_t})$ is given by

$$p(y_t | Y_{t-1}, X_t, s_t) = \begin{cases} f(y_t | Y_{t-1}, X_t, \theta_1) & \text{if } s_t = 1 \\ \vdots \\ f(y_t | Y_{t-1}, X_t, \theta_M) & \text{if } s_t = M \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

where $p(y_t | Y_{t-1}, X_t, s_t)$ is the probability density function conditional upon the history of the process, $Y_{t-1} = \{y_{t-i}\}_{i=1}^\infty$, some exogenous variables $X_{t-1} = \{x_{t-i}\}_{i=1}^\infty$ and the regime variable s_t while θ_m is the vector of parameters present in regime m . The development of the MS-VAR models works with the assumption that s_t is generated by a hidden discrete-state homogenous and ergodic Markov chain given as

$$\Pr(s_t | S_{t-1}, Y_{t-1}, X_t) = \Pr(s_t | s_{t-1}; \rho) \quad (3)$$

The transition probability is then defined by

$$p_j = \Pr(s_{t+1} = j | s_t = i) \quad (4)$$

The MS-VAR model can then be categorized into two major models: the mean model and the intercept model. In the mean models, there is a once-and-for-all shift in the times series given as

$$y_t - \mu(s_t) = A_1(s_t)(y_{t-1} - \mu(s_{t-1})) + \dots + A_p(s_t)(y_{t-p} - \mu(s_{t-p})) + u_t \quad (5)$$

In the intercept models, there is a smooth and gradual adjustment in the times series given as

$$y_t = \alpha(s_t) + A_1(s_t)y_{t-1} + \dots + A_p(s_t)y_{t-p} + u_t \quad (6)$$

Under each model category, eight different model combination is possible depending on which of the estimated parameters are permitted to vary as shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Markov Switching VAR Models.

		MSM		MSI	
		μ varying	μ invariant	μ varying	μ invariant
A_j invariant	\sum invariant	MSM-VAR	Linear-VAR	MSI-VAR	Linear-VAR
	\sum varying	MSMH-VAR	MSH-VAR	MSIH-VAR	MSH-VAR
A_j varying	\sum invariant	MSMAR-VAR	MSA-VAR	MSIAR-VAR	MSA-VAR
	\sum varying	MSMARH-VAR	MSAH-VAR	MSIARH-VAR	MSAH-VAR

Source: Krolzig, (1997) where \sum = Heteroscedasticity parameter ,

3.2 Data Sources

The data for this study was sourced from the CBN statistical bulletin 2022. The data set are in quarterly frequency covering between 2010 and 2022. This period was selected due to availability of quarterly data that captured the two most recent economic recessions (2016 and 2020) in Nigeria where there is high growth and low growth regimes. More so, the option

of conversion of annual data to quarterly data as many have done in the past to obtain large samples eliminates important features of the data generating process and hence throws up inconsistent statistical interpretation (Ginsburgh, 1973). The variables include the Real Gross Domestic Product (RGDP), Oil sector output (OIL), Nonoil sector output (NOIL) and Money Supply (M2). In this study, the aggregated non-oil sector is made up 3 key sectors (Agric, Manufacturing and Trade). Usually, quarterly data incorporates seasonal components. Thus, the data set for this study exhibited seasonal fluctuation in quarterly patterns which may affect the statistical interpretation of the parameters. To remove this pattern, Census X-13 method (US Census Bureau, 2017) was used to seasonally adjust the log of the series.

4. Empirical Result

4.1 Test for Stationarity

The condition for the estimation of a MS-VAR model is that the variables to be included in the model must be stationary. We employed the Augmented Dick-Fuller (Dickey & Fuller, 1979) unit root test to confirm the stationarity of the selected time series. Table 2 present the result of the ADF unit root test.

Table 2: ADF Unit Root Test Result

Variable	ADF Statistic			
	Level	Prob	1 st Difference	Prob
RGDP	-2.556883	0.1086	-6.565188	0.0000
OIL	-0.521203	0.8782	-9.966659	0.0000
NOIL	-1.870342	0.6552	-6.785917	0.0000
M2	-1.302736	0.8759	-5.120610	0.0001

The ADF unit root test result indicate that all the series for this study are unit root processes but first difference stationary. Thus the model of this study was estimated based on I(1) time series processes.

4.2 Determination of Model

The MS-VAR model can be categorized into two major models: the mean model and the intercept model. Under each model category, eight different model combination is possible depending on which of the estimated parameters are permitted to vary as shown in Table 1. In the mean models, there is a once-and-for-all shift in the times series whereas in the intercept models, there is a smooth and gradual adjustment in the times series. A plot of the logged seasonally adjusted series alongside their rate of change is presented in Figure 3. A close observation of the plot reveal that the series follows a Markov Switching VAR intercept model with smooth transitions. In order to determine the particular model to estimate, all the eight Markov Switching VAR intercept models were estimated and the model with the minimum lag order information criteria and maximum likelihood of estimation was selected. From all the estimated model with unique standard error and covariance matrix, 2 lag lengths was suitable for this study as determined by Akaike Information Criterion of 16 and Schwarz Criterion of 20 with a likelihood of -318. For brevity, we did not include the table. In this case, a Markov Switching VAR model where all parameters are allowed to vary was selected. That is Markov Switching Intercept Auto-Regressive Heteroscedastic (2) –VAR(2) [MSIARH(2) –VAR(2)] model.

Figure 3: Log of Seasonally Adjusted Series and Rate of Change

MSIARH(2) –VAR(2) Result

Table 3 shows the estimated parameters of the MSIARH(2) –VAR(2) model. We concentrated on the GDP model to interpret and discuss the result based on each regime. The estimated intercept parameters of the GDP model were variant in each regime. The intercept indicated the baseline level of GDP at steady state. In regime 1, the intercept is negative (-0.5583) which is against theoretical predictions. However, a plausible explanation of this implies that the initial transition parameter conditional on regime 1 shows the likelihood of recovery. The intercept parameter in regime 2 is positive (0.36492). Again, this parameter implies that the initial transition parameter conditional on other estimated parameters is positive but showing the 36 percent likelihood of a short-lived regime. In this model, there is evidence of variation in the regime-specific coefficient which explains the relationship between variable changes across different states. In regime 1, the estimated parameter of the first lag of non-oil sector is positive (0.00386) and statistically significant which corroborates the findings of Akighir & Tarlumun, (2019) who found a positive relationship between non-oil sector and growth. However, this relationship became negative (-0.0764) as the model transitions to regime 2. This result implies that the previous quarter's non-oil sector output contributes only about 0.3 percent to economic growth in the high growth regime. The coefficient of the non-oil sector of -0.0764 indicate that as the economy transitions to the low growth regime, the non-oil sector which was supposed to drive the growth recovery leads to a fall in the GDP of about 7 percent. This further indicate the lack of a robust non-oil sector to drive economic growth in Nigeria. This underscores the need for economic diversification. In regime 1, the estimated parameter of the first lag of oil sector is positive (1.2047) but statistically insignificant while it is negative in regime 2 with a statistically significant value of -0.0326. this implies that both oil and non-oil sectors are negatively related to economic growth in a low growth regime. The positive relation between oil sector and growth reinforces the finding of Nwosu et al., (2018) who found positive relationship between oil and industrial production.

Table 3: Estimated Parameters of MSIARH(2) –VAR(2)

	Regime 1				Regime 2			
	GDP	M2	NOIL	OIL	GDP	M2	NOIL	OIL
Intercept	-0.5583 (0.2685)	-0.8467 (0.3497)	-0.4621 (0.2189)	-0.0809* (0.9794)	0.36483 (0.1820)	-0.3860* (0.3252)	0.2738* (0.5087)	3.6374 (1.4741)
Regime Dependent Autoregressive Parameter								
GDP(-1)	-0.1137* (0.0936)	0.05197* (0.1226)	-0.0860* (0.0765)	0.02849* (0.3436)	-0.1286 (0.0531)	0.98074 (0.0949)	-0.0753* (0.1484)	-2.1967 (0.4300)
GDP(-2)	0.08873* (0.1093)	0.32915 (0.1427)	0.20933 (0.0892)	-0.3887* (0.3996)	0.01658* (0.0582)	-0.5598 (0.1037)	-0.1601* (0.1622)	-1.1690 (0.4703)
M2(-1)	0.28463 (0.2888)	-0.1363* (0.3663)	0.00879* (0.2317)	1.12426* (1.0182)	0.10485* (0.1157)	-0.6427 (0.2049)	-0.0559* (0.3199)	-0.1759* (0.9299)
M2(-2)	-0.3117* (0.3234)	1.42250 (0.4243)	-0.4622* (0.2643)	0.50907* (1.1871)	0.0316* (0.0847)	0.2007* (0.1513)	0.0078* (0.2367)	0.6825* (0.6857)
NOIL(-1)	0.00386* (0.0395)	0.10247 (0.0513)	0.02247* (0.0321)	-0.4932 (0.1438)	-0.0764 (0.0235)	-0.0474* (0.0419)	-0.1315 (0.0654)	-0.8814 (0.1900)
NOIL(-2)	-0.0178* (0.0454)	0.37354 (0.0595)	0.03258* (0.0371)	-0.3224* (0.1667)	0.0088* (0.0188)	-0.0336* (0.0336)	-0.0829* (0.0525)	0.38143 (0.1523)
OIL(-1)	1.2047 (0.4492)	-1.6337 (0.5882)	0.8264 (0.3669)	3.3178 (1.6464)	-0.0326* (0.0952)	-0.2058* (0.1697)	0.2844* (0.2655)	-0.5760* (0.7694)
OIL(-2)	-0.167* (0.5551)	1.5392 (0.7250)	0.1142* (0.4530)	-5.0644 (2.0309)	0.7729 (0.2164)	3.2136 (0.3853)	1.2960 (0.6024)	5.9914 (1.7469)

Note: Standard error (). * 0.05 level of significance

The positive relationship between both oil and non-oil sectors in the high growth regime as well as the negative relationship in the low growth regime agrees with structural transformation theory that suggest that economic diversification contribute positively to sustained growth while the reverse is the case for undiversified economy (Syrquin, 1988).

Regime Dependent Heteroscedasticity Parameter								
	Regime 1				Regime 2			
SIGMA-GDP	1.2904 (0.3713)	-0.6810* (0.3716)	0.9436 (0.2879)	-0.5019* (0.9683)	0.2276 (0.0647)	0.0386* (0.0821)	0.1803* (0.1331)	-0.1477* (0.3725)
SIGMA-M2	-0.6810 (0.3716)	2.2113 (0.6376)	-0.3046* (0.2884)	-1.7089* (1.3096)	0.0386* (0.0821)	0.7262 (0.2065)	-0.7616 (0.2751)	0.7775* (0.6798)
SIGMA-NOIL	0.9436 (0.2879)	-0.3046* (0.2884)	0.8618 (0.2482)	-1.0514* (0.8159)	0.1803* (0.1331)	-0.7616 (0.2751)	1.7773 (0.5063)	-3.8929 (1.2990)
SIGMA-OIL	-0.5019* (0.9683)	-1.7089* (1.3096)	-1.0514* (0.8159)	17.380 (5.0066)	-0.1477* (0.3725)	0.7775* (0.6798)	-3.8929 (1.2990)	14.912 (4.2425)

Note: Standard error (). * 0.05 level of significance

The regime dependent heteroscedasticity indicates regime-specific volatility or variability of the variables. The result implies a non-constant error variance in each regime. It is expected that there should be low volatility in high growth of regime 1 in GDP. Thus, the Non-oil sector volatility parameter is positive (0.9436) and very high which indicate the higher uncertainty of staying in economic growth though statistically insignificant. The oil sector volatility parameter is negative (-0.5019) and statistically significant. This indicate the lower tendency of staying in economic growth in regime 1. Expectedly, in regime 2, the volatility parameter of non-oil parameter is smaller and positive (0.1803) but statistically significant in the low growth regime. The oil sector volatility parameter is negative (-0.1477) and statistically significant. Again, this also indicate the lower tendency of contributing to economic growth in regime 2.

Table 4 shows the regime switching probabilities. The result indicates that the probability that the economy will remain in regime 1 (high growth regime) is 53.4 percent while the probability that the economy will remain in regime 2 (low growth regime) is 55 percent. However, the probability of switching from regime 1 to regime 2 is 46.5 percent while the probability of switching from regime 2 to regime 1 is 45.1 percent. The estimated duration of the economy in the high growth regime is two quarters and one month (7 months) while the estimated duration of the economy in the low growth regime is two quarters and two month (8months). The analysis reveals that there is higher tendency of the economy to fall into recession because of a low growth persistence in the economy. The result further indicates that there is more likelihood of that the economy will switch from high growth regime to low growth regime with longer low growth duration in the low growth state. This finding is contrary to Balcilar et al., (2017) who found higher growth persistence in South Africa. Due to the structure of Nigerian economy, this transitioning tendencies is enhanced by the competing role of the two broad sectors of oil and non-oil sectors which exposes Nigerian economy to incessant economic shocks.

Table 4: Probability of Regime Switching.

	Regime 1	Regime 2	Duration
Regime 1	0.534438	0.465562	2.15
Regime 2	0.451162	0.548838	2.21

The regime-specific probability map of MSIARH(2) –VAR(2) model is shown in Figures 4 and 5. This shows the filtered and smoothed probability under the two state mechanisms. The essence is to compare the evolution of each state by the filtered probability and the smoothed probability. The standard judgement in this case is that: if the smoothed probability of a particular state mechanism in a specific quarter is more than 0.5, it implies that there is elements of volatility of economic growth in that state mechanism. From these figures, the smoothed probability is above 0.5 which confirm the presence of state evolutions in each regime. This tends to reveal two recent economic recessions (2016 and 2020) in Nigeria in the sample period.

Figures 6 and 7 shows the response of the variables to one standard deviation shocks to the

MSIARH(2) –VAR(2) model of this study within 10 quarters forecast horizon. Figure 6 shows that GDP begins to respond to shock to oil and non-oil sectors from the fourth quarter in regime 1. A one standard deviation shock to non-oil sector will cause a very small increase in economic growth in the fourth quarter but the effect is short-lived as it becomes negative by the seventh quarter. However, in regime 1, one standard deviation shock to oil sector at impact causes a decrease in GDP. But the negative impact in GDP is overturned by the seventh quarter and remained above the steady state value throughout the 10 quarters forecast horizon.

Figure 6: Impulse Response Function of Regime 1.

Unlike regime 1, Figure 7 shows that in regime 2, GDP begins to respond to shock to oil and non-oil sectors from the first quarter. A one standard deviation shock to non-oil sector causes a very small increase in economic growth in the first quarter but the effect becomes negative by the third quarter and recovers by the eighth quarter. However, in regime 2, one standard deviation shock to oil sector at impact causes a small increase in GDP. The increase becomes significant in seventh quarter before decreasing again by the 8th quarter. However, by the ninth quarter, the response of GDP to both the oil and non-oil sectors increased and remained above the steady value throughout the 10 quarters forecast horizon.

Figure 7: Impulse Response Function of Regime 2.

5. Policy Implication of the Study and Conclusion

As Nigeria strives towards economic diversification, it is crucial to implement policies that strengthens the interdependences between oil and non-oil sectors without neglecting their individual importance in the economy. This is because of the finding that both oil and non-oil sectors positively contribute to high economic growth. Thus, there is need for policy-makers to intensify efforts towards utilizing revenue from oil sector to promote and support the expansion of non-oil sectors' growth through targeted initiatives, incentives and investments. Furthermore, this study identified two distinct regimes-high and low- growth. This support the existence of cyclical movement in the Nigeria's growth trajectory which requires the implementation of stabilization policies in low growth regimes. Policy-makers should therefore, implement measures to enhance sustained economic stability. These measures should include counter-cyclical fiscal policies, targeted interventions in key sectors like the agricultural and manufacturing sectors and improvement of export commodities besides oil to mitigate the impacts of external shock. Finally, the existence of incessant business cycle indicates that the economy is prone to shocks which support the need for a long term economic planning. The study found that there is low growth persistence in the economy and higher rate of movement from high growth to low growth. The policy-makers should therefore not only focus on short-term recoveries but equally address other factors that contribute to the transition between the regimes. This will require a comprehensive economic development strategy that considers both short-term and long-term objectives. To conclude, this study focused on the impact of oil and non-oil sectors output on economic growth in Nigeria through the lens of a Markov-switching VAR Analysis. Quarterly data on oil sector output and aggregate non-oil sector output and money supply was utilized for the estimation in a two regime model- regime 1 (high growth) and regime 2 (low growth). The result indicated that the GDP displays significant levels of transition from high growth regime to low growth regime. We found that previous values

of both oil and non-oil sectors are positively related to high economic growth in regime 1 while previous values of both oil and non-oil sectors are negatively related to low economic growth. The probability of staying in regime 1 is 53.4 percent while the probability of staying in regime 2 is 55 percent. This shows higher tendency to deep into recession through a low growth persistence in the economy. The result also indicates that there is more likelihood of switching from high growth regime to low growth regime with longer low growth duration. This transitioning tendencies is enhanced by the competing role of the two broad sectors of oil and non-oil sectors which exposes Nigerian economy to incessant economic shocks. Based on our findings, we recommend that the government should prioritize the development of the non-oil sectors. This will reduce the excessive dependence on oil revenue and curtail the effect of oil price shocks on the economy. There should be increased investment in the non-oil sectors particularly the manufacturing and agricultural sectors to harness their potentials to drive economic growth which will in turn strengthen non-oil exports and revenue to the government. Even though this study was restricted to asymmetric impact of oil and non-oil output on economic growth, other areas of research can be explored to a nuanced understanding of the interrelatedness of various sectors. Other research areas may include analysis of sectoral dynamics to identify targeted areas of policy making for different regimes; investigation of impact of external shocks on identified growth regimes and assessing the effectiveness of extant policy aimed at diversification in different regimes

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